

Studies on the Solution Equilibria of Heteroligand Binuclear Chelates of Some Transition Metals with Diethylenetriaminepentaacetic Acid as the Primary and Diamines as the Secondary Ligand

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Mixed ligand chelates of the type M_2LA_2 , where $M(II) = Cu(II), Ni(II)$ or $Zn(II)$, $L =$ diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid (DTPA) and $A =$ ethylenediamine (en) or 1,2-propanediamine (pn) have been investigated potentiometrically. Evidences are provided for the formation of binuclear mixed ligand chelates by the addition of the secondary ligand (A) to the binary complex M_2L . Formation constants of the resulting binuclear ternary species have been determined at $25 \pm 1^\circ$ ($\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$).

THE solution equilibria of binuclear simple and mixed ligand complexes of some transition metals using different physico-chemical techniques, such as potentiometry and spectrophotometry¹⁻⁴, have been studied. In an earlier communication⁵ the results of potentiometric studies on the systems $M(II)$ -DTPA-tiron were reported. The work has been further extended on the systems $M(II)$ -DTPA-en/pn, and the results of these studies are presented in this communication (DTPA = diethylenetriaminepentaacetic acid, en = ethylenediamine, pn = 1,2-propanediamine).

Experimental

All chemicals used were either of B.D.H., A.R. or E. Merck, G.R. grade. Stock solutions of metal nitrates and tetrapotassium salt of DTPA (Fluka) were prepared as described earlier⁵. Ethylenediamine (en) and 1,2-propanediamine (pn) were used as their dihydrochlorides. Concentration of all the solutions was checked potentiometrically.

pH measurements were carried out with a Philips pH meter (PR 9405 M), having a working accuracy of ± 0.02 , using standard glass (PV 9011) and calomel (PV 9021) electrodes. The instrument was standardised against 0.05 M potassium hydrogenphthalate for pH 4 at $25 \pm 1^\circ$. The total volume (50 ml), ionic strength ($\mu = 0.1 M KNO_3$) and concentration of ligand L ($5 \times 10^{-3} M$) and metal ion and ligand A ($10 \times 10^{-3} M$) were kept constant at the beginning of the titration. Each titration was performed in duplicate to establish the reproducibility of the results.

Calculations :

The acid dissociation constants of the diaminedihydrochlorides (pK_1 and pK_2) of en_2H^+ (7.08, 9.78) and pn_2H^+ (6.96, 9.82) were calculated by the method of Chaberek and Martell⁶.

The formation constants for 2 : 1 : 1 and 2 : 1 : 2, $M(II)$ -DTPA-en/pn chelates have been evaluated by the methods discussed in detail in our earlier communication⁵, according to which

(i) $\log K_{M_2LA_2}^{M_2L}$, between $m = 1$ and 5 is calculated as :

$$\log K_{M_2LA_2}^{M_2L} = \frac{T_M - [A].X}{[A]^2.X}$$

here,

$[A]$ = free ligand concentration

$$[A] = \frac{2T_M - T_{OH} - [H^+] + [OH^-]}{2[H^+]^2/K_1K_2 + [H^+]/K_2}$$

$$X = [H^+]^2/K_1K_2 + [H^+]/K_2 + 1$$

where T_{OH} = base used per mole of ligand

(ii) Between $m = 1$ and 3, and 3 and 5,

$$\log K_{M_2LA_2}^{M_2L} \text{ or } \log K_{M_2LA_2}^{M_2LA} = \frac{T_A - [A^{2-}].X}{T_A.[A^{2-}] + (A^{2-})^2.X}$$

$$\text{where } [A^{2-}] = \frac{2T_A - aT_A - [H^+] + [OH^-]}{2[H^+]^2/K_1K_2 + [H^+]/K_2}$$

$$X = [H^+]^2/K_1K_2 + [H^+]/K_2 + 1$$

Results and Discussion

Only the curves representing the system $Cu(II)$ -DTPA-en is given in Fig. 1 as representative ones. The curves for the systems $Cu(II)$ -DTPA-pn, $Ni(II)$ / $Zn(II)$ -DTPA-en/pn being identical in nature, have been omitted for the sake of brevity.

Curve a (Fig. 1) illustrates the potentiometric titration of tetrapotassium salt of diethylenetriamine- N,N',N'',N''' -pentaacetate. Nonlabile nature of the remaining carboxy proton of tetrapotassium salt of DTPA even at a high pH is indicated by the absence of an expected inflection at $m = 1$.

a=DTPA, b=en.2H⁺, c=1:1 Cu(II)-DTPA, d=2:1 Cu(II)-DTPA, e=2:1:2 Cu(II)-DTPA-en, T=theoretical composite curve and → appearance of ppt.

Fig. 1. System 2:1:2 Cu(II)-DTPA-en.

Curve b (Fig. 1) representing the titration of dihydrochloride of en.2H⁺, exhibits an ill-defined inflection at $m=1$ (where m =moles of base added per mole of metal ion or ligand), which may be attributed to the titration of only one of the protons of the dihydrochloride. As the other proton of the dihydrochloride is made labile only on complex formation, no further inflection at $m=2$ is observed when the free dihydrochloride is titrated.

A well defined inflection at $m=1$ in curve c (Fig. 1) representing the pH-metric titration of 1:1 Cu(II)-DTPA and non-formation of the heterogeneous phase during the titration may probably be attributed to the formation of a stable soluble 1:1 Cu(II)-DTPA species. The larger initial lowering of the pH exhibited by the curve d for 2:1 Cu(II)-DTPA system in comparison to that shown by the 1:1 Cu(II)-DTPA system (curve c) and a well defined inflection at $m=1$ may be ascribed to the formation of a 2:1 Cu(II)-DTPA species which, however, appears to undergo disproportionation giving soluble stable 1:1 Cu(II)-DTPA complex and metal hydroxide as has been reported earlier⁵. An additional inflection at $m=3$ (pH ~8) in the curve d

may be ascribed to the disproportionation of the 2:1 species.

Curve e (Fig. 1) illustrating the titration of 2:1:2 Cu(II)-DTPA-en system runs very close to curve d upto $m=1$ and this may be attributed to the initial formation of 2:1 Cu(II)-DTPA species. Another inflection at $m=5$ preceded by a long buffer region may be correlated to the addition of the secondary ligand en to the initially formed 2:1 Cu(II)-DTPA complex resulting in the formation of a soluble 2:1:2 Cu(II)-DTPA-en species.

The formation of 2:1:2 Cu(II)-DTPA-en species may occur by either (i) the simultaneous addition of both the secondary ligand molecules to the initially formed 2:1 Cu(II)-DTPA species or (ii) by the addition of secondary ligand (en) molecules in two overlapping steps.

Analysis of the data given in Table 1 reveals that by considering the mode (i), the values of formation constants (column 1) are not within the limits of permitted variations and, therefore, the possibility of formation of mixed ligand binuclear species by mode (i) can be completely ruled out. However, the applicable constancy observed in the values of $\log K_{M_2LA}^{M_2L}$ and $\log K_{M_2LA_2}^{M_2LA}$ by considering the mode (ii) undoubtedly supports the addition of diamine molecules in two overlapping steps resulting in the formation of a soluble 2:1:2 M_2LA_2 species through the intermediate 2:1:1 M_2LA species.

TABLE 1—Cu(II)-DTPA-en

m	pH	TABLE 1—Cu(II)-DTPA-en			
		2:1:2 (1)	2:1:1 (2)	2:1:1 +0:0:1 (3)	
1.2	4.45	18.75		9.06	
1.4	4.65	18.38		9.08	
1.6	4.80	17.99		8.99	
1.8	4.95	17.62		8.91	
2.0	5.05	17.41		8.92	
2.2	5.15	17.19		8.93	
2.4	5.22	17.09		9.02	
2.6	5.30	16.95		9.13	
2.8	5.38	16.81		9.37*	
3.0	5.44	16.76			
3.2	5.50	16.62			
3.4	5.58	16.57	$\log K_{M_2LA}^{M_2L}$	9.02 ± 0.11	
3.6	5.66	16.50		7.00	
3.8	5.76	16.30		7.30	
4.0	5.88	16.18		7.30	
4.2	6.01	16.09		7.25	
4.4	6.26	16.46		7.25	
		$\log K_{M_2LA_2}^{M_2L}$	17.41 ± 1.33	$\log K_{M_2LA_2}^{M_2LA}$	7.15 ± 0.15

* Values omitted.

TABLE 2—FORMATION CONSTANTS OF MIXED LIGAND CHELATES AT 25 ± 1°

System	Equilibrium quotient		
	$\frac{[M_2LA_2]}{[M_2L][A]^2}$	$\frac{[M_2LA]}{[M_2L][A]}$	$\frac{[M_2LA_2]}{[M_2LA][A]}$
Cu(II)-DTPA-en/pn	17.41 ± 1.33	9.02 ± 0.11	7.15 ± 0.15
Cu(II)-DTPA-pn	16.57 ± 1.95	9.04 ± 0.12	6.95 ± 0.11
Ni(II)-DTPA-en	12.45 ± 2.43	7.14 ± 0.13	3.85 ± 0.14
Ni(II)-DTPA-pn	12.38 ± 3.00	7.45 ± 0.10	4.22 ± 0.18
Zn(II)-DTPA-en	12.14 ± 1.32	6.57 ± 0.10	4.24 ± 0.16
Zn(II)-DTPA-pn	12.15 ± 1.73	6.89 ± 0.10	4.23 ± 0.17

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